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SALT TOLERANCE IN WILD RICES

M. Akbar, K. K. Jena & D. V. Seshu
International Rice Research Institute, Manila, Philippines

Seven wild species of *Oryza* and the African cultivated species *O. glaberrima* were evaluated for salt tolerance using water culture techniques in the Phytotron glasshouse at 29°/21°C (day/night) and 70% relative humidity. The *O. sativa* cultivars Nona Bokra and IR28 were the tolerant and susceptible checks. Seedlings at the 2-3 leaf stage were subjected to salt stress of 6800 ppm (EC 12dS/m) by adding 1:1 mixture of NaCl and CaCl₂ to the nutrient solution. Salinization continued for 14 days. All species tested were susceptible to salinity during the seedling stage (see table). Survival, ranged from zero for *O. brachyantha* to 16% for *O. glaberrima*. The tolerant check, Nona Bokra showed 100% survival, whereas there was no survival of seedlings in the susceptible check, IR28. Thus, search for tolerance to salinity among the wild species tested and in the cultivated species, *O. glaberrima* for levels higher than in Nona Bokra or as alternate sources may not be fruitful.

Survival of *Oryza* species at 6800 ppm (EC 12dS/m) salinity.

<i>Oryza</i> Species	Accession No.	Genome	Seedlings tested (no.)	Seedlings that survived (no.)	Survival %
<u><i>O. glaberrima</i></u>	100855	AA	25	4	16.0
<u><i>O. nivara</i></u>	102163	AA	21	3	14.3
<u><i>O. punctata</i></u>	101434	BB	60	5	8.3
<u><i>O. officinalis</i></u>	100896	CC	88	5	5.7
<u><i>O. minuta</i></u>	101125	BBCC	55	7	12.7
<u><i>O. latifolia</i></u>	100885	CCDD	46	6	13.0
<u><i>O. latifolia</i></u>	100914	CCDD	28	4	14.3
<u><i>O. australiensis</i></u>	100882	EE	54	1	1.9
<u><i>O. brachyantha</i></u>	100115	FF	43	0	0
Nona Bokra (tolerant check)		AA	60	60	100
IR28 (susceptible check)		AA	60	0	0